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**Exploring Unitary Distributives in Classical Nahuatl: Key or Share Markers?
Explorando los distributivos unitarios en náhuatl clásico: ¿marcadores de clave o de
cuota?**

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the reduplicated unitary numeral *se:sem* in Classical Nahuatl. In the literature, reduplicated numerals in Classical Nahuatl have been claimed to be distributive numerals. However, in some cases, reduplicated unitary numerals display two behaviors that one would not expect from a distributive numeral: 1) they seem to mark the distribution key rather than the share, and 2) they seem to induce referential covariation of a simple indefinite. Despite these two observed behaviors, we argue that the reduplicated unitary numeral in Classical Nahuatl is a standard distributive numeral, since –unlike key markers– it does not multiply distributive relations. We propose that reduplicated unitary numerals in Classical Nahuatl are always under the scope of a null distributive operator that quantifies universally over a plurality. Furthermore, we claim that, in all cases, unitary reduplicated numerals in Classical Nahuatl covary with respect to the entities quantified by the null distributive operator. This study aims to contribute to a better understanding of distributive numerals, particularly to the debate of whether in some languages, such as Nahuatl, the distributive unitary numeral marks the key rather than the share of distribution.

RESUMEN

En este estudio analizamos el numeral unitario reduplicado *se:sem* en náhuatl clásico. En la bibliografía, se ha afirmado que los numerales reduplicados en náhuatl clásico son numerales distributivos. Sin embargo, en algunos casos, los numerales unitarios reduplicados muestran dos comportamientos que no se esperarían de un numeral distributivo: (1) parecen marcar la clave de distribución en lugar de la parte distribuida y (2) parecen inducir la covariación referencial de un indefinido simple. A pesar de estas dos observaciones, en este trabajo argumentamos que el numeral unitario reduplicado en náhuatl clásico es un numeral distributivo estándar, ya que —a diferencia de los marcadores de clave— no multiplica las relaciones distributivas. Proponemos que los

numerales unitarios reduplicados en náhuatl clásico están siempre bajo el alcance de un operador distributivo nulo que cuantifica universalmente sobre una pluralidad. Además, sostenemos que, en todos los casos, los numerales unitarios reduplicados en náhuatl clásico covarían con respecto a las entidades cuantificadas por dicho operador distributivo nulo. Este trabajo busca contribuir a una mejor comprensión de los numerales distributivos, en particular con respecto al debate sobre si, en algunas lenguas como el náhuatl, el numeral unitario distributivo marca la clave y no la parte distribuida de la distribución.

KEYWORDS

Distributive numerals. Universal quantifiers. Reduplication. Classical Nahuatl. Semantics.

PALABRAS CLAVE

Numerales distributivos. Cuantificadores universales. Reduplicación. Náhuatl clásico. Semántica.

LAY SUMMARY

This paper investigates the semantics of the reduplicated unitary numeral *se:sem* in Classical Nahuatl from a formal perspective. In the literature, reduplicated numerals in Classical Nahuatl have been claimed to be distributive numerals. However, in some cases, they behave in an unexpected way for a distributive numeral. For instance, sometimes they seem to mark the key and not the share of the distribution. In distributive relations, the key consists of the individuals, events, or places across all of which the share is distributed, while the share is a property that holds of each individual, event, or place comprising the key (for example, [*Every girl*]_{KEY} [*ate four apples*]_{SHARE}). The behavior of *se:sem* in such cases is unexpected from a distributive numeral, since, across languages, distributive numerals are share markers, not key markers. Despite this seemingly anomalous behavior, we argue that, in Classical Nahuatl, reduplicated unitary numerals are standard distributive numerals that always mark the share of a distributive relation. We base our claim on the

fact that, unlike true key markers, reduplicated unitary numerals in Classical Nahuatl do not multiply distributive relations when they occur multiple times in a single clause.

INTRODUCTION

This paper presents an analysis of the distributive unitary numeral in Classical Nahuatl (CN) *se:sem*, which is formed through the reduplication of the unitary cardinal *sem-*. Our main claim is that, despite showing a seemingly puzzling behavior, *se:sem* is a standard distributive numeral that marks the distribution share, as any other reduplicated numeral in CN.

As we will show, the use of *se:sem* raises several interesting challenges for the semantic theory of distributive numerals for at least two reasons. First, in some cases, it seems to introduce the distributive key, which is not expected of a distributive numeral, since, following Gil (1982, pp. 339–341), distributive numerals always introduce the share. In example (1), note how *se:semilwitl* ‘each day/daily’ appears to correspond to the distributive key, over which the share is distributed, *in kiawi* ‘the way in which it rains.’¹

- (1) cēcemilhuitl in quiahui
se:~sem-ilwitl in kiawi
DISTR~one-day.ABS DET rain
‘Everyday/Daily is the way that it rains’ (Carochi, 2001[1645], p. 390, f. 107)

Second, there are also cases in which the reduplicated unitary numeral (RUN or RUNS in plural, hereafter) seems to have scope over an indefinite. In the most plausible reading, the indefinite is interpreted as if its reference covaries with respect to the RUN (*n* per each

¹ Our examples are presented in at least four lines. In the first, we register the orthographic representation of the linguistic expression as it appears in the original source. In the second line, we present a morphological segmentation in the IPA. The third line contains the gloss. Then, in the fourth line, a free translation and citation of the source of the example are offered. In some cases, we have added some context which helps to interpret the example. When the example was too long, we added space between the lines to ease reading. We employ the symbol \approx to indicate the most plausible interpretation of an utterance in a given context. The symbols \checkmark and \times indicate that an utterance is, respectively, acceptable or unacceptable in the context (see Tonhauer; Matthewson, 2016). Finally, as requested by one reviewer, in some examples we have also added the logical form for each alternative interpretation (see § 4).

one). This behavior is unexpected from a distributive numeral, since, as claimed by Gil (1982, pp. 118–128) and Kuhn (2019, pp. 6–7), distributive numerals cannot introduce referential covariation of an indefinite under their scope. We illustrate this with example (2), where the indefinites (in this case ‘three’ and ‘four canoes’) under the scope of the distributive *se:semilwitl* ‘each day’ covary referentially with respect to it: ‘3 or 4 (different) canoes per day’.

- (2) in cecemilhuitl popoliuia, ačo eacalli anočo naoacalli
in **se:~sem-ilwi-tl** poʔ~poliwia aʔso
 DET DISTR~one-day-ABS PLR~finish.PST.IPFV maybe
e:-a:kal-li anoʔso **na:w-a:kal-li**
 three-canoe-ABS or.perhaps four-canoe-ABS
 ‘Perhaps three canoes (of water) or perhaps four canoes (of water) were consumed every day’ (FC09, Sahagún, 1959, p. 48, f. 38r)

It has been noted that in some Mesoamerican languages, unitary distributive numerals behave differently from other distributive numerals analyzed in the literature. For example, according to the analyses by Gómez González (2023) for Matlatzinca and by Chapa and Vázquez Rojas Maldonado (2024) for Ocotepéc Zoque, in these languages the unitary distributive can, in some instances, introduce the key of the distribution, thus providing counterexamples to Gil’s proposal.

However, in this paper, we will argue that in NC, *se:sem* never introduces the key, but rather, it is a standard distributive numeral that always introduces the share. We arrive at this conclusion on the basis of cases with more than one occurrence of *se:sem* in which, nonetheless, the distributive relations are not multiplied.

To support our analysis, we provide examples in which *se:sem* does not display the behavior expected of a quantifier marking the key. Furthermore, we present cases in which its behavior aligns with what is expected of a share marker. To account for the instances in which the RUN seems to be introducing the key (examples 1 and 2), we will propose the presence of a null distributive operator, as has been done in the case of Korean (Oh, 2001, 2006, pp. 22–85).

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. First, we present some general information about the language, the corpus, and the evidence (§1) and provide some background on distributive numerals in natural languages (§2). We then discuss the morphology of reduplicated numerals in CN (§3), and further, we elaborate on their description and interpretation, focusing on RUNS (§4). Next, we present our analysis of RUNS in CN (§5). Finally, we present some conclusions of our study (§6).

1. THE LANGUAGE, THE CORPUS, AND THE EVIDENCE

Classical Nahuatl is an Uto-Aztecan language from the Nahuan branch. It is a pro-drop language with nominative-accusative alignment and an unmarked VSO order (Dakin, 2021, p. 2177, Table 1; Launey, 1992, pp. 19–23, 33–40, among others). In general, the term “Classical Nahuatl” refers to the written form of the Nahuatl varieties of the Valley of Mexico, mainly from the 16th and 17th centuries (Canger, 1978a, Map 1, 1978b, pp. 4–6, 1980, Map 1, 1988, pp. 45–47; Flores Farfán, 2010, pp. 189–196).

To describe the use of *se:sem* in CN, we compiled a corpus based mainly on the *Florentine Codex* (FC), books 1–12, as well as some additional data from the *Testaments of Culhuacán* (TC, 1984) and the collection of documents in Anderson, Berdan and Lockhart (BC, 1976), all from the 16th century.² To retrieve the occurrences of RUNS in the FC, we conducted a query on books 1–12 in the electronic corpus of Thouvenot and Fisher ([s.d.]). The corpus size is 251,115 words, in which we have documented 135 cases of RUNS.

Before proceeding to the description of distributive numerals in CN, it is essential to consider the following two points. First, we must note that this study has exclusively qualitative purposes. We are interested in describing the use of *se:sem* in the corpus to propose a semantic analysis and discuss how its semantics and distribution contribute to our understanding of the typology of distributive numerals. A quantitative analysis of this form would undoubtedly be interesting; however, it is beyond the scope of this study.

² See D’olwer and Cline (1973) for more details on the FC.

Second, the nature of the language under study (a written language of the 16th and 17th centuries) comes with a series of methodological challenges for semantic analyses, most notably the absence of negative evidence (corpora only offer positive evidence) and the impossibility of accessing acceptability judgments. Thus, following a common practice in historical linguistics, our analysis assumes that the data extracted from a corpus are grammatical, true, and felicitous linguistic expressions in the context in which they are uttered. By contrast, since the absence of evidence does not imply evidence of absence, if a linguistic expression is not documented in a corpus, it is not possible to determine whether it is an acceptable or unacceptable linguistic expression in the language under study. Finally, based on the Uniformitarian Principle, according to which “the rules that govern language structure today are the same that governed language structure yesterday and will be the same that will govern language structure tomorrow”, we assume that typological generalizations can serve as hypotheses in light of which to evaluate the data extracted from our corpus (see Croft, 1994; Walkden, 2019).

2. WHAT IS A DISTRIBUTIVE NUMERAL?

Following Cable (2014, p. 563, ex. 1), we adopt the definition in (3) of a distributive numeral:

- (3) DISTRIBUTIVE NUMERAL: A morphosyntactic construction containing a numeral, whereby (i) the sentence as a whole receives a distributive reading, and (ii) under the allowable readings, the numeral contained within the construction must be interpreted AS IF it is within the scope of a distributive operator.

We will now briefly explain each component of Cable’s definition. The first part of the definition refers to the distributive interpretation. In a clause with a distributive interpretation, a predicate applies to each and every minimal part of a plurality (or to each and every member of a set). The plurality whose members the predicate applies to is called the *distributive key*. The predicate that applies to the members of that plurality is referred to as the *distributive share* (Balusu, 2006, pp. 1–2; Champollion, 2019, p. 290; Choe, 1987, pp. 74–134; Zimmermann, 2002, p. 322). Let us look at an example. The sentence in (4) is

compatible with a distributive interpretation, shown in (4a), in which *bought a ball* is predicated of every child, so that each child bought a (possibly different) ball. Additionally, the sentence has a collective interpretation (4c), in which no distributive relation is established: (4a), in its collective reading, is true when a group of children together bought a single ball.

- (4) a. The kids bought a ball.
 b. Distributive interpretation: [The kids]_{KEY} [bought a ball]_{SHARE} each.
 $[\forall x.x \in \iota X.KIDS(X)]_{KEY} \rightarrow [\exists y. BALL(y) \ \& \ 1-ATOM(y) \ \& \ BOUGHT(x,y)]_{SHARE}$
 c. Collective interpretation: The kids together bought a ball.

There are different types of keys depending on the entities that comprise the plurality. If the key consists of a plurality of temporally distinct events, a TEMPORAL KEY is obtained. In (5a), for example, the key is a plurality of events ('leaving the classroom') in which, for each one, three children left the room. In turn, a SPATIAL KEY is composed of a plurality of locations, as shown in (5b), where the key contains a plurality of spatially distinct corrals, each containing five piglets. Finally, a PARTICIPANT KEY consists of a plurality of individuals, in which the key is expressed by an argument of the clause. For example, in (5c), the key consists of a plurality of children, each of whom was given three different piglets to feed (Balusu, 2006, pp. 1–2; Cable, 2014, p. 564; Gil, 1982, pp. 11–31; Vázquez Rojas Maldonado, 2013, pp. 90–93).³

- (5) Types of distribution keys.
 a. TEMPORAL KEY: The children left the room three by three.
 Interpretation: 'In each temporally distinct event, it is true that three children left.'

³ Balusu (2006, pp. 7–13) suggests that, in distributive relations, the key is always made up of events and that the different types of keys result from the way events are delimited. If the events are temporally distinct, we have a temporal key ("one event per moment"). When events occur in different locations, we have a spatial key ("one event per location"). In turn, we obtain a participant key when each of the individuals in the denotation of a co-argument defines a different event ("one event per participant"). However, here we will not follow Balusu's proposal, since, according to Pereltsvaig (2012), in several languages distributivity over participants is grammatically coded in a different way from distributivity over events. Thus, it is not clear whether it is possible to reduce participant keys to event keys.

- b. SPATIAL KEY: In each corral, there are five piglets.
Interpretation: ‘In each distinct corral, it is true that there are five pigs.’
- c. PARTICIPANT KEY: Each child fed three piglets.
Interpretation: ‘For each distinct child, it is true that she fed three pigs.’

The second part of Cable’s (2014) definition concerns the scope of the distributive operator: a distributive operator DIST universally quantifies the minimal parts that make up a plurality and assigns a property P to each of them (6) (Cable, 2014, p. 563; Champollion, 2019, pp. 293–294; Choe, 1987, pp. 74–134; Lasersohn, 1995, pp. 86–87; Link, 1998, p. 109, ex. 48; Schwarzschild, 1996, p. 61). For example, in the distributive reading of (4a), a distributive operator assigns the property ‘to buy a ball’ to each and every child that composes a plural individual, such that it is true for each child that they bought a ball (4b). The domain over which the distributive operator universally quantifies is called the RESTRICTOR, and the assigned property is called the SCOPE. Thus, in (4b), the restriction corresponds to a plurality made up of children, and the scope to the property of buying a ball. From the second part of the definition in (3), it follows that distributive numerals are always part of the expression corresponding to the distributed share, since for a numeral to be distributive, it must always be interpreted as if it were within the scope of a distributive operator (Gil, 1982, pp. 339–341).

$$(6) \quad \llbracket \text{DIST} \rrbracket = \lambda P_{\langle e, t \rangle}: \lambda y_e: \forall x. [x \leq y \ \& \ \text{atom}(x)]_{\text{RESTRICTOR}} \rightarrow [P(x)]_{\text{SCOPE}}$$

(Cable, 2014, p. 563, ex. 2)

Let us now examine how distributive numerals in natural language align with the definition in (3). Consider the case of Purepecha, where distributive numerals are marked with the suffix *-ntani*. Thus, for example, in (7) *tsimantani* is a distributive numeral meaning ‘two for each one’.

- (7) Purepecha (Isolate)
- | | | |
|--------|-----------|--------------------------|
| Nanaka | sapi-echa | jikwa-ra-s-ø-ti=ksï |
| girl | little-PL | bathe-CAUS-PFVO-3IND=3PL |

tsima-ntani	wichu	sapirati-echa-ni
two-DIST	dog	little-PL-OBJ

‘The girls each bathed two puppies.’
(Vázquez Rojas Maldonado, 2013, p. 91, ex. 8)

First, note that, according to Vázquez Rojas Maldonado (2013, p. 91), (7) has a strictly distributive interpretation. In this example, the predicate ‘to bath two puppies’ applies to each and every member of a plurality of girls. The share corresponds to the predicate ‘to bath two puppies.’ The key, in turn, corresponds to the plurality of girls, since each and every girl bathed two different dogs. Second, in Vázquez Rojas analysis, the numeral *tsimantani* must be interpreted as if it were within the scope of a distributive operator: each girl (*nanaka sapiecha* ‘little girls’) is assigned the property of having bathed two dogs (*jikwarastiksi tsimantani wichu sapiratiechani* ‘they bathed two dogs’). In other words, in (7), *tsimantani* would be located within the scope of a distributive operator, while the restrictor would correspond to a plurality denoted by the girls (*nanaka sapiecha*). Thus, in Purepecha, a numeral with the suffix *-ntani* fulfills all the features of distributive numerals, as per the definition in (3).

Before moving on to CN data, let us stress that distributive numerals are not the only quantifiers that force a distributive reading of the clause in which they appear. Other types of quantifiers also introduce distributive interpretations. However, these quantifiers typically mark the key, not the share. An example of such a quantifier is the universal quantifier *every* in English (see Gil, 1995 for the different types of universal quantifiers that introduce distributive interpretations).

3. REDUPLICATED NUMERALS IN CLASSICAL NAHUATL

Before addressing numeral reduplication in CN, we provide a brief description of the generalities of the CN numeral system in terms of Greenberg (1990[1978]).⁴ In Table 1, we

⁴ For further information on the CN numeral system, we direct the reader to the references cited here. Note that the data of this section has been taken from sources where the authors’ purpose is merely to record or describe the numeral system of CN. This is to say that, although we take the data from the cited sources, the labels we have employed here (e.g. ‘free’ vs ‘bound’ form) do not necessarily correspond to the terminology used in those sources.

register the simple atoms of the CN numeral system, that is, the basic numerals that are not bases and that are not the result of an arithmetical operation coded by linguistic means. Note that some simple atoms have free and bound forms, whereas others have only a bound form.

Free	Bound	Number value
/se:/	/sem-/	1 ⁵
/o:me/	/o:m/	2
/e:ji/	/e:-/ ~ /e:j-/	3
/na:wi/	/na:w-/	4
	/ma:kwi:l-/	5
	/tʃik ^w -/	
	/maʔtʃak-/	10
	/kaʃto:l-/	15

Table 1. Simple atoms

Based on Andrews (2003, pp. 307–318), Launey (1986, pp. 663–684, 1992, pp. 63–70), Molina (2013[1571], pt. 1, ff. 118v–121v) and Olmos (1875[1547], p. 191). See also Herrera Jiménez (2026).

In the numeral system of CN, there are two arithmetical operations whereby it is possible to form complex numerals: addition and multiplication by a vigesimal base (Andrews, 2003, pp. 307–318; Herrera Jiménez, 2023, §4.4; Launey, 1986, pp. 663–684, 1992, pp. 63–70; Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, ff. 118v–121v; Olmos, 1875[1547], pp. 190–191). In CN, there are several strategies to perform the addition operation. First, the numerals 6–9 are compounds in which the simple atoms 1–4 are added to the numeral /tʃik^w-/ ‘5’ (8). The numeral /tʃik^w-/ cannot stand alone and only appears as part of the

⁵ In CN, the numeral ‘one’ also displays some of the properties of an indefinite article (Herrera Jiménez; Pozas Loyo, 2025).

compound numerals 6–9 (Andrews, 2003, pp. 307–318; Launey, 1986, pp. 663–684, 1992, pp. 63–70).

- (8) chicunauī
 tʃik^w-na:wi
 five-four
 ‘nine’ (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, f. 118v)

Second, in CN, it is also possible to add two numerals by linking them either by affixation of the prefix /om-/ to the second summand (9a) or by using a superessive (9b) or comitative link (9c) (Andrews, 2003, pp. 307–318; Launey, 1986, pp. 663–684, 1992, pp. 63–70; Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, ff. 118v-121v; Olmos, 1875[1547], pp. 190–191).

- (9) a. matlactlionnauī
 maʔtlak-tʃi **on**-na:wi
 ten-ABS plus-four
 ‘ten plus four’ (10+4=14) (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, f. 118v)
- b. Centzuntli ymammatlaccpoualli
 sen-tʃon-tʃi **i:-pan** maʔtlak-po:wal-li
 one-four.hundred-ABS POSR.3SG-on ten-twenty-ABS
 ‘two hundred on top of four hundred’ (1*400+10*20=600)
 (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, f. 119v)
- c. cempōhualli on-cactolli ihuān ēyi
 sem-po:wal-li on-kafto:l-li **i:-wa:n** e:ji
 one-twenty-ABS plus-fifteen-ABS POSR.3SG-with three
 ‘Three with twenty plus fifteen’ (3+(1*20+15)=38)
 (Launey, 1986, p. 666, ex. 824)

It is also possible to form complex numerals by multiplying a numeral, the multiplier, by a vigesimal base, which functions as the multiplicand. The multiplier is always a numeral of a lower value than the vigesimal base. Vigesimal bases always appear as the second element of a compound in which the first element is one of the numerals 1–10 or 15 (10). There is also a sporadic product, *tʃamik* ‘20’, which does not behave as a standard base, that is, it does not appear as the multiplicand in any other product (Andrews, 2003,

pp. 307–318; Launey, 1986, pp. 663–684, 1992, pp. 63–70; Molina, 2013 [1571], pt. 1, ff. 118v-121v; Olmos, 1875[1547], pp. 190–191).

- (10) ompoualli
 o:m-po:wal-li
 two-twenty-ABS
 ‘forty’ (2*20=40) (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, f. 119r)

There is a small set of numeral classifiers that always attach to a numeral as the second element of a compound, as shown in (11) for the classifier /te-/. These classifiers are homophonous to other forms that appear in nouns and verbs without a counting classificatory function (Andrews, 2003, pp. 307–318; Launey, 1986, pp. 663–684, 1992, pp. 63–70, 236–238; Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, ff. 118v-121v; Olmos, 1875[1547], pp. 190–194; Stolz, 2018).

- (11) ōn-te-mê cuācuāuhtin
 o:n-te-me? k^wa:~k^wa:w-tin
 two-CL-PL PL~eagles-PL
 ‘two eagles’
 (FC08, Sahagún, 1979b, p. 8, f. 6r) apud (Launey, 1986, p. 674, ex. 876)

In CN, reduplicated numerals can be interpreted as distributive numerals. Reduplication is a morphophonological operation that copies and duplicates or reproduces material (Inkelas; Downing, 2015, p. 502; Rubino, 2013). The form from which material is copied is called the BASE, while the sequence that reproduces the phonological features taken from the base is called the REDUPLICANT (McCarthy; Prince, 1993, p. 66). To illustrate this, consider examples (12) and (13). In (12a), we show the free form of numeral ‘4’, and in (12b), the reduplicated form of this numeral. As can be seen by contrasting (12a) with (12b), the base of reduplication is the numeral *na:wi* (‘4’), while the reduplicant corresponds to the sequence *na:*, since it contains the material copied from the base (*na:wi*). In (13), we show the same process for the numeral ‘2’ (Launey, 1986, pp. 680–681).

- (12) a. naui
na:wi
four
'four' (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, f. 118v)
- b. nanau
na:~na:wi
DISTR~four
'four by four/four each' (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, f. 119r)
- (13) a. ome
o:me
'two' (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, f. 118v)
- b. oome
o:~o:me
DISTR-two
'two by two/two each' (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, f. 119r)

Note that the base of reduplication can be a root or a morphological constituent larger than a root (see Haugen, 2011, pp. 12–13). Additive numerals formed through compounding provide evidence in favor of this hypothesis. For example, in (14), the reduplication operation can either separately copy phonological material from each of the simple roots of the compound (14a) or from the compound as a whole (14b).

- (14) a. chichicunanaui
 $\widehat{tʃi}:\sim\widehat{tʃik}^w\sim na:\sim na:wi$
DISTR-five-DISTR-four
'nine by nine/nine each' (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, f. 120r)
- b. Chichiconau
 $\widehat{tʃi}:\sim\widehat{tʃik}^w-na:wi$
DISTR-five-four
'nine by nine/nine each' (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 2, f. 19v)

The behavior of the numeral *maʔtlaktli* '10' when subject to reduplication also constitutes an argument for considering that, in CN numerals, the base of reduplication can be a root (Herrera Jiménez, 2023, §8.3). Diachronically, *maʔtlaktli* appears to stem from

the compounding of the roots *maʔ-* ‘hand’ and *tʰak-* ‘torso’ (Andrews, 2003, p. 310; Launey, 1986, pp. 560–561). When reduplicated, this numeral copies and reproduces material from the segment *tʰak-*, one of the roots of the presumed compound from which *maʔtʰaktʰi* is etymologically derived. To account for this, one could assume that the morphological component does recognize the presence of the roots *maʔ-* and *tʰak-*, even though synchronically, the meaning of *maʔtʰaktʰi* ‘10’ does not seem compositionally derived from the combination of these roots. In this case, the reduplication operation would take the root *tʰak-* as its base. Therefore, we take (15b) as evidence that in CN, numeral reduplication can take a root as its base.

- (15) a. *matlactli*
 maʔtʰak-tʰi
 ten-ABS
 ‘ten’ (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, f. 118v)
- b. *matlatlactli*
 maʔ~tʰa:~tʰak-tʰi
 ten~DISTR~diez-ABS
 ‘ten by ten/ten each’ (Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 1, f. 120r)

In CN numerals, the reduplicant is always a heavy bimoraic syllable (for an Uto-Aztec perspective, see Haugen, 2008, pp. 35–50). However, it is not clear whether the reduplicant in numerals is always a (C)V:-type syllable or whether it can alternate between a (C)V: and a (C)V? syllable. Launey (1986, pp. 680–681) and Andrews (2003, p. 317) argue that the reduplicant can take either the form (C)V: or (C)V?. For Launey (1986), the reduplicant is of the form (C)V: when the reduplicated numeral begins with a consonant, as in (12b) above. In contrast, the reduplicant appears as (C)V? if the reduplicated numeral starts with a vowel, which would be the case in (13b). Andrews (2003), on the other hand, proposes that both types of reduplicant can occur with all numerals. However, according to him, there is a semantic difference between reduplicated numerals with the (C)V: pattern and those with the (C)V? pattern. The (C)V: pattern expresses distributivity (‘*n* to each’), while the (C)V? pattern signals repetition or grouping (‘by *n*’s’ or ‘in groups of *n*’) (see

also Carochi, 2001[1645], pp. 264–281, ff. 70-75v). In contrast, for Launey (1992, pp. 257–266), in reduplicated numerals, the reduplicant always follows the (C)V: pattern. As shown in examples (12–15), we adopt Launey’s (1992) position for the proposed phonetic transcription.⁶

Finally, it should be noted that the reduplication operation can be iterated (Andrews, 2003, pp. 230–231; Carochi, 2001[1645], pp. 266–270, ff. 70v-72; Launey, 1986, pp. 681, 1031). In (16), for example, the reduplicated numeral expression *na:na:na:wi* ‘four by four/four to each’ undergoes the reduplication operation twice.

- (16) mochi tlacatl nananavi ic qujnmjna in mjtl
 motʃi tla:katl **na:~na:~na:wi** ik
 all man/person.ABS DISTR~DISTR~four thus
 k-in-mi:na in mi:tʃ
 O.3-O.PL-shot.with.arrow DET arrow.ABS
 ‘Every man is shot with four arrows each.’
 (FC10, Sahagún, 1961, p. 172, f. 121v apud Launey, 1986, p. 681, ej. 923)

4. THE SEMANTICS OF REDUPLICATED NUMERALS IN CLASSICAL NAHUATL

As mentioned earlier, in CN, reduplicated numerals can be interpreted as distributive numerals (see Andrews, 2003, p. 317; Launey, 1986, pp. 680–681, 1992, pp. 257–258), that is, they behave as expected from the definition of distributive numerals in (3). In this section, we first explore the contexts in which we would expect a standard distributive numeral to occur (§4.1). Based on this, we claim that in CN, reduplicated numerals may display the properties of a normal distributive numeral. Then, we will look at some cases where a RUN should not appear if it were a standard distributive numeral (§4.2). Despite this, we conclude that the best account for the behavior of CN RUN is one in which they are treated as standard distributive numerals (§4.3).

⁶ In most sources, long vowels and the glottal stop are not represented orthographically. Thus, we do not have sufficient evidence to determine whether the reduplication pattern is (C)V: or (C)V?. Besides, as we have mentioned, in CN there is no agreement on whether reduplicated numerals can exhibit both patterns. Hence, for simplicity, we have decided to transcribe all reduplicated numerals by means of the (C)V: pattern.

4.1. Reduplicated numerals as standard distributive-share markers

Let us first introduce an example (17) from a 16th-century CN text in which we find the reduplicated numeral *maʔt̩la:t̩lakmat̩* ‘ten *mat̩* for each one’:

- (17) Context: Pedro de Paz, a councilor of Coyoacán, divides the lands of Julián Uixtopolcatl between Ana, Julián’s daughter, and Francisca, Julián’s niece.

matlatlacmatl	concuic pa ^{oc} x matl concui franca no x matl concui ynnana
maʔ~t̩la:t̩lak~ma-t̩	k-onk ^{wi} -ʔ ik pat̩la:wak x
ten~RED~ten-arm-ABS	O.3-take-s.PL thus wide ten
mat̩	k-on-k ^{wi} fransiskaʔ no: x
arm.ABS	O.3-DIR-take Francisca also ten
mat̩	k-on-k ^{wi} in anaʔ
arm.ABS	O.3-DIR-take DET Ana

‘(They, Ana and Francisca,) take 10 matl (of land) each. Francisca takes 10 matl of width, and Ana also takes 10 matl.’ (BC, Anderson; Berdan; Lockhart, 1976, p. 90, doc. 10)

$\forall x [x \in \text{Ana} \oplus \text{Francisca} \ \& \ \text{ATOM}(x) \rightarrow \exists y [\text{LAND}(y) \ \& \ 10\text{-MATL}(y) \ \& \ \text{TAKE}(x, y)]]$

In (17), *maʔt̩la:t̩lakmat̩* behaves as expected from a distributive numeral, according to Cable’s (2014) definition. First, *maʔt̩la:t̩lakmat̩* appears in a clause with a distributive interpretation: the predicate ‘take 10 *mat̩*’ applies to each and every member of the group composed of Ana and Francisca. The subsequent context indicates that this is the correct reading of (17), as it is explicitly stated that Ana takes 10 *mat̩* of land and Francisca does as well. Second, in this example, the reduplicated numerical expression *maʔt̩la:t̩lakmat̩* is interpreted as being within the scope of a distributive operator. Specifically, *maʔt̩la:t̩lakmat̩* is part of the predicate assigned to each of the minimal parts of a plurality: the one composed of Ana and Francisca. In other words, in (17), each of the individuals that make up the subject plurality, Ana and Francisca, takes 10 *mat̩* of land. Note that in (17), the distributive key (that is, Ana and Francisca) corresponds to a participant key.

However, as Launey (1986, pp. 680–681) shows, in NC, the distributive key may also be spatial, as in (18), or temporal, as in (19).⁷

- (18) aço mamacuiltin anoço chichiquacemme, anoço matlatlactin momana
 aʔso **ma:~ma:kʷil-tin** aʔnoso **tʃi:~tʃikʷase:-meʔ** aʔnoso
 perhaps DISTR~five-PL or.perhaps DISTR~six-PL or.perhaps
maʔ~tʃla:~tʃlak-tin mo-mana-ʔ
 ten~DISTR~ten-PL REFL.2/3-lay.down-S.PL
 ‘(The women) sort themselves in groups of five, or perhaps six or perhaps ten’
 (FC09, Sahagún, 1959, p. 41, f. 33r apud Launey, 1986, p. 680, ej. 922)

- (19) aço çan cecen in ticqujxtiz
 aʔso san **se:~sen** in ti-k-ki:ʃti:s
 perhaps only DISTR-uno DET S.2SG-O.3-get.out.CAUS.FUT
 ‘Maybe, you will pass them (the sticks) through one by one’
 (FC01, Sahagún, 1970, p. 25, f. 9v apud Launey, 1986, p. 681, ej. 920)

Note that, in several instances, RUNs also show the typical traits of a standard distributive numeral, as shown in (19) and (39) in §5.2.

4.2. Two puzzles on the distribution of RUNs in Classical Nahuatl

Once we have reviewed the main characteristics of reduplicated numerals in CN, let us turn to the reduplicated form of the unitary numeral and its behavior, which –potentially– poses a challenge for the typology of distributive numerals in natural languages. As mentioned above, in CN, the RUN *se:sem* behaves in a way that would not be expected if it were a distributive numeral. On the one hand, in some cases, it seems to mark the distribution key, rather than the share; on the other hand, when a simple indefinite is within scope, its

⁷ As one reviewer points out, it may be the case that example (18) is not spatially distributive, but simply cohesion between the singularities that comprise a plurality of five, six or ten women. However, it may also be true that cohesion results from the spatial arrangement between these pluralities, i.e. from the fact that these pluralities fill a different space from each other. We do not have enough evidence to argue against or in favor of one of these hypotheses.

reference can covary with that of the RUN.⁸ We will now examine these two facts in more detail.

4.2.1. RUNs as purported key markers

We will first refer to the cases in which *se:sem* seems to be a key instead of a share marker. Consider example (20), in which we find a RUN in the compound word *se:semilwitl* ‘every/each day’. There are two logically possible interpretations of (20). In the first interpretation, *se:semilwitl* marks the share, as in any distributive numerical expression. Under this reading, each of the rain events (*in kiawi*) is assigned a day, so the meaning of the sentence could be paraphrased as ‘Each rain event occurs on a day.’ In the second interpretation, *se:semilwitl* marks the key, such that each day is assigned a rain event. We could paraphrase this second reading as follows: ‘every day/daily a rain event occurs.’ We consider this second reading to be the most plausible explanation. In addition to the first reading being rather uninformative, Carochi (2001[1645], p. 390, f. 107) also points out that the expression *se:semilwitl* is equivalent to *mo:mo:stlae?* ‘each day/daily’ and that, in fact, one could substitute one for the other in (20) without any change in meaning (see also Molina, 2013[1571], pt. 2, f. 59r).

(20) cēcemilhuitl in quiahui

se:~sem-ilwitl in kiawi
 DISTR~one-day.ABS DET rain

‘Everyday/Daily is the way that it rains’ (Carochi, 2001[1645], p. 390, f. 107)

Interpretation 1: Every rain event occurs on a day

$\forall e [\text{RAIN}(e) \rightarrow \exists e' [1\text{-DAY}(e') \ \& \ e \subseteq_{\text{TEMPORALLY}} e']]$

Interpretation 2: Every day, a rain event occurs $\forall e$

⁸ It is worth noting that authors do not give the same treatment to the RUN in modern varieties of Nahuatl. For instance, in Tezcoco Nahuatl, Peralta Ramírez (1991, p. 7) translates *se?sen* as ‘uno a cada uno’ (‘one to each one’), which suggests that *se?sen* is a standard distributive numeral. By contrast, Flores Nájera (2019, pp. 163–180) claims that, in Tlaxcala Nahuatl, *sehsen* ‘cada uno’ (‘each one’) is a universal quantifier. However, according to Flores Nájera (2019), it is not clear if *sehsen* is formed by reduplicating the unitary cardinal, since numeral reduplication does not seem to be a productive process in Tlaxcala Nahuatl anymore. For other modern varieties of Nahuatl, see Beller and Beller (1979, p. 254), Brockway (1979, p. 166), Canger (1981, p. 36), Sischo (1979, p. 347) and Tuggy (1979, p. 74).

$$\forall e [1\text{-DAY}(e) \rightarrow \exists e' [\text{RAIN}(e') \ \& \ e' \subseteq_{\text{TEMPORALLY}} e]]^9$$

In (21), we present another example in which the RUN seems to introduce the key and not the share: a small basket of shelled corn (*t̄lao:lli sents̄inkopinka:to:n̄t̄li*) and one hundred ears of corn (*ma:ma:kwilpo:walli sint̄li*) are assigned to each person (*in se:sen t̄la:katt̄*). In this example, it appears that the set of people corresponds to the key and the ears of corn to the share.

(21) njman ie tlaolli cen tzincopincatontli, yoan mamacuilpoalli cintli, in cecen tlacatl, quinextiaia

niman	ye	t̄lao:l-li	sen-t̄sinkopinka:to:n-t̄li
then	already	shelled.maize-ABS	one-little.basket-ABS
i:-wa:n		ma:~ma:k̄wil-po:wal-li	sin-t̄li
POSR.3SG-with		DISTR~five-twenty-ABS	corn-cob-ABS
in	se:~sen	t̄la:katt̄	ki-neftia:ja
DET	DISTR~one	man/person.ABS	O.3-make.appear.PST.IPFV

‘then, what each person produced was a small basket of shelled corn and one hundred ears of corn’ (FC03, Sahagún, 1978, p. 7, f. 5r)

Examples like (20–21) potentially constitute counterexamples to the proposals of Gil (1982) and Cable (2014), who argue that distributive numerals always express the share (i.e., they are interpreted as if they were within the scope of a distributive operator). As we have already noted, the possibility that the distributive form of the unit numeral can mark the distributive key has been suggested for other languages, such as Matlatzinca (Gómez González, 2023) and Ocotepc Zoque (Chapa Barrios; Vázquez Rojas Maldonado, 2024).¹⁰ In Ocotepc Zoque, distributed numerals are marked by reduplication. In this language, the

⁹ For the purposes of this paper, we model TEMPORAL INCLUSION ($\subseteq_{\text{temporally}}$) as a membership relation that holds between a set of events E just in case there is an isomorphism $f: \langle E, \subseteq_{\text{temporally}} \rangle \rightarrow \langle T, \subseteq \rangle$, where T is a set of temporal segments.

(i) TEMPORAL INCLUSION
 $\forall e \forall e': e \in E \ \& \ e' \in E. e \subseteq_{\text{temporally}} e' \leftrightarrow f(e') \subseteq f(e)$

¹⁰ See also Royer (2022, p. 36, note 6) for Chuj.

RUN *tumä-tumä* can mark the share (Context 1) or the key (Context 2) with non-temporal nouns, as shown in (22) (Chapa Barrios; Vázquez Rojas Maldonado, 2024).

(22) Ocotepc Zoque (Mixe-Zoque)

Context 1: In a small party with 5 children there are different kinds of candies which all children ate. Each of the five children liked one different kind of candy.

Context 2: In a small party with 5 children there are different kinds of candies which all children ate. All five children liked each kind of candy.

te' une'ista'm nyä'omyaju tumtumä pa'ak
 te' une='is=ta'm y-nä'om-yaj-u **tumä-tumä** pa'ak
 DET child=ERG=PL 3A-enjoy-3PL-CP one-one candy
 'Each children enjoyed a (different) candy'
 'The children enjoyed each candy'

True in context 1 and 2

(Chapa Barrios; Vázquez Rojas Maldonado, 2024, p. 16, ex. 11)

However, when *tumä-tumä* modifies a temporal noun, such as *ame'* 'year' in (23), the RUN can only mark the key (Chapa Barrios; Vázquez Rojas Maldonado, 2024).

(23) Ocotepc Zoque (Mixe-Zoque)

tumtumä ame' mijtyajpa te' yomota'm
tumä-tumä **ame'** mit-yaj-pa te' yomo=ta'm
 one-one year come-3PL-ICP DET woman=PL
 'Every year the women come'.

Key reading: For every consecutive year there is an event of the women coming to visit.

Share readings:

NOT: For every woman there is a different year in which she visits

NOT: For every visit of the women there is a different year in which it occurs

(Chapa Barrios; Vázquez Rojas Maldonado, 2024, p. 11, ex. 7)

As for Matlatzinca, the numeral 'one' *werá* does not behave as a standard distributive numeral when prefixed by *pu-*. For instance, in (24), *puwerá* seems to be interpreted as if it were in the restrictor of a distributive operator (Context 1) rather than in its scope

(Context 2). In the acceptable reading of (24), *puwerá* marks the key, and the share consists of a plurality of sitting events. By contrast, in the unacceptable reading of (24), *puwerá* marks the share and the key comprises a plurality of sitting events (Gómez González, 2023, pp. 23–33).

(24) Matlatzinca (Oto-Manguéan)

Context 1: There are four chairs and four girls. Each girl is seated on one of the four chairs (one chair per girl).

Context 2: There are four chairs and four girls. Three girls are seated on one of the four chairs (one chair per each one of these three girls). There is one empty chair and one girl standing.

Pu-werá we=toxuwí ku=chorí
 DISTR-one CL=girl 3SG.INCOM=be.seated
 ‘Each girl is seated.’

Acceptable in Context 1. Unacceptable in Context 2.
 (Gómez González, 2023, p. 28, ex. 16)

4.2.2. *Referential covariation of simple indefinites under the scope of RUNs*

Now, we focus on cases where the RUN seems to induce the covariation of a simple indefinite under its scope. To illustrate this, we return to example (21). There are at least two possible interpretations of (21), as shown in (25). In one interpretation (25a), the reference of the simple indefinite *t̂lao:lli sent̂sinkopinka:to:n̂t̂li* ‘1 small basket of shelled corn’ does not covary with respect to the reference of *se:sen t̂la:katt̂* ‘each person’; that is, there is a single basket of corn that is given by all the people (either together or in separate events). In another interpretation (25b), the denotation of *t̂lao:lli sent̂sinkopinka:to:n̂t̂li* varies according to that of *se:sen t̂la:katt̂*. Thus, the interpretation would be that there is a different basket of corn for each person, and each person hands over a different basket of corn. In our view, the second interpretation is the most plausible, and the Spanish version of this passage seems to confirm this impression.

(25) Interpretations of (21)

a. There is only one basket of shelled corn, and every person delivered that same basket of shelled corn and one hundred ears of corn.

$\exists x [1\text{-BASKET}(x) \ \& \ \text{SHELLED-CORN}(x) \ \& \ \forall y [\text{PERSON}(y) \ \& \ \text{ATOM}(y) \ \rightarrow \ \text{DELIVER}(y,x) \ \& \ \exists z [100\text{-ATOM}(z) \ \& \ \text{CORN-EAR}(z) \ \& \ \text{DELIVER}(y, z)]]]$

b. For every person, there is one basket of shelled corn and one hundred ears of corn, such that each person delivers a different basket of shelled corn and groups of one hundred different ears of corn. \forall

$\forall y [\text{PERSON}(y) \ \& \ \text{ATOM}(y) \ \rightarrow \ \exists x [1\text{-BASKET}(x) \ \& \ \text{SHELLED-CORN}(x) \ \& \ \text{DELIVER}(y,x) \ \& \ \exists z [100\text{-ATOM}(z) \ \& \ \text{CORN-EAR}(z) \ \& \ \text{DELIVER}(y,z)]]]$

In (26), we present another example in which the denotation of a simple indefinite, *e:a:kalli* ‘three canoes (of water)’ / *na:wa:kalli* ‘four canoes (of water)’, seems to covary with that of a RUN, *se:semilwitl* ‘each day’. As in the previous example, we consider that it is possible to interpret (26) in at least two ways.¹¹ In the first reading, the denotation of *e:a:kalli* and *na:wa:kalli* does not covary with that of *se:semilwitl*. Thus, in this interpretation, there are no different groups of three or four canoes for each day, but only three or four canoes of water, and those same canoes were consumed each day. In the second reading, the denotation of *e:a:kalli* and *na:wa:kalli* does covary with that of *se:semilwitl*. Consequently, each day, there are different groups of three or four canoes that are consumed. Once again, we consider this second interpretation to be the most plausible.¹²

(26)	in	cecemilhuitl	popoliuia,	aço	eacalli	anoço	naoacalli
	in	se:~sem-ilwi-tl			po?~poliwia		a?so
	DET	DISTR~one-day-ABS	PLR~finish.PST.IPFV				perhaps
	e:-a:kal-li		ano?so		na:w-a:kal-li		

¹¹There is a third possible interpretation in which *se:semilwitl* ‘each day’ is distributed among groups of three or four canoes (of water). This reading could be paraphrased as follows: for each of the canoes in a group of three or four canoes, it is true that each of the canoes in such a group was consumed in one day. However, we do not consider this interpretation to be the most plausible in this context.

¹² In example (26), the pluractional verb *po?poliwia* does not seem to induce the covariation of the simple indefinites *e:a:kalli* and *na:wa:kalli*. According to Kuhn (2019, pp. 6–7), in natural languages pluractional verbs do not induce the covariation of a simple indefinite within their scope. Thus, in (26), it would be equally unexpected for *po?poliwia* to induce the covariation of *e:a:kalli* and *na:wa:kalli*.

three-canoe-ABS or.perhaps four-canoe-ABS
‘Perhaps three canoes (of water) or perhaps four canoes (of water) were consumed each day’ (FC09, Sahagún, 1959, p. 48, f. 38r)

Interpretation 1: There were perhaps three or four canoes of water, and, for each day, these same three or four canoes of water were consumed.

Interpretation 2: For each day, there were perhaps three or four canoes of water, and each day, different groups of three or four canoes of water were consumed. \exists ¹³

Following Gil (1982, pp. 118–128) and Kuhn (2019, pp. 6–7, 15), the fact that the RUN in CN can induce covariation in the reference of a simple indefinite would be unexpected if the RUN were a distributive numeral.¹⁴ Take, for instance, example (27a) of

¹³ We present a formal representation of the two possible interpretations of this example in (40).

¹⁴ One of the reviewers has pointed out that, in examples (21) and (26), canoes and baskets are measure-uses of a container noun, and that, in (17), *maß* is clearly a measure. Therefore, it may be the case that these expressions are not indefinites. Then, if the measures in (21) and (26) are not indefinites, it is not necessarily unexpected that they can covary with respect to the RUN. We acknowledge that it is not possible to rule out an analysis according to which, in CN, measure phrases are not indefinites, which in turn may explain why a RUN may induce covariation on them. However, we argue that our analysis is supported by the behavior of measures in other languages, as we show in the following examples in which measure phrases and indefinite behave alike. For instance, in Spanish, a measure phrase such as *dos kilotonos de dinamita* ‘two kilotons of TNT’ multiplies when it is under the scope of a distributive universal quantifier that marks the distribution key (i). Thus, Spanish measure phrases behave in the same way as indefinites when they interact with a distributive universal quantifier (i–ii). Note also that, in Spanish, measure phrases do not multiply when they are under the scope of a pluractional operator such as the frequentative periphrasis *andar + gerund* (iii) (Laca, 2006). This is another context in which measure phrases and indefinites align (iii–iv). Hence, we argue that CN measure phrases may behave in the same way as the Spanish ones, provided that the behavior of the latter can be extrapolated cross-linguistically.

- (i) [Cada mes]_{KEY} explotan [dos kilotonos de dinamita]_{SHARE}
‘Every month two kilotons of TNT explode.’
Natural reading: Different portions of 2 kilotons TNT explode every month.
 $\forall e [1\text{-MONTH}(e) \rightarrow \exists y [\text{TNT}(y) \ \& \ 2\text{-KT}(y) \ \& \ \text{EXPLODE}(y, e)]]$
Non-sensical-reading: The same portion of 2 kilotons of TNT explode every month.
 $\exists y [\text{TNT}(y) \ \& \ 2\text{-KT}(y) \ \& \ \forall e [1\text{-MONTH}(e) \rightarrow \text{EXPLODE}(y, e)]]$
- (ii) [Cada mes]_{KEY} explotan [dos bombas]_{SHARE}
‘Every month two bombs explode.’
Natural reading: Two different bombs every month.
 $\forall e [1\text{-MONTH}(e) \rightarrow \exists y [\text{BOMB}(y) \ \& \ 2\text{-ATOM}(y) \ \& \ \text{EXPLODE}(y, e)]]$
Non-sensical-reading: The same two bombs explode every month.
 $\exists y [\text{BOMB}(y) \ \& \ 2\text{-ATOM}(y) \ \& \ \forall e [1\text{-MONTH}(x) \ \& \ \text{EXPLODE}(y, e)]]$
- (ii) #Andan explotando dos kilotonos de dinamita.
Non-sensical reading: ‘Two kilotons of TNT keep exploding.’
 $\exists E [\forall e' [e' \in E \rightarrow \exists y [\text{TNT}(y) \ \& \ 2\text{-KT}(y) \ \& \ \text{EXPLODE}(y, e')]]]$

Turkish, in which, according to Gil (1982), the only possible interpretation is that different groups of two men carry the same three suitcases. This interpretation reflects the fact that the distributive form of the cardinal 2 (*ikişer*) in (27a) cannot induce the covariation of the indefinite three *üç bavul* ‘three suitcases.’ To obtain the reading with covariation of the indefinite, in Turkish, the distributive form of the cardinal 3 (*üçer*) must be used (27b). The behavior of the distributives shown in (27) is also attested by Gil (1982, pp. 118–128) for other languages such as Tagalog, Georgian, and Romanian.

- (27) a. **İkişer** adam **üç** bavul taşıdı
 two.DISTR man three suitcase carried
 (Gil, 1982, p. 119, ex. 21b)
 Interpretation: ‘Different sets of two men carried the same three suitcases
 in one or more events’
- b. **İkişer** adam **üçer** bavul taşıdı
 two.DISTR man three.DISTR suitcase carried
 (Gil, 1982, p. 125, ex. 28c)
 Interpretation: ‘There are at least two sets of two men and at least two sets
 of three suitcases. Each group of two men carried at least one group of three
 suitcases and each group of three suitcases was carried by at least one group
 of two men’ (covariation allowed)

Notice that the same behavior attested in CN for simple indefinites under the scope RUNS is also reported for indefinites scoping under *pu*-marked unitary numerals in Matlatzinca. As previously mentioned, in Matlatzinca, a unitary numeral prefixed by *pu*-always seems to mark the key. In addition, the denotation of a simple indefinite may covary when it occurs under the scope of a *pu*-marked unitary numeral. In (28), for instance, the denotation of *nan pelota* ‘one ball’ covaries with respect to that of *puwerá wetowá’a* ‘each boy’ (Gómez González, 2023, pp. 32–33).¹⁵

(iv) #Andan explotando dos bombas.
 Non-sensical reading: ‘Two bombs keep exploding.’
 $\exists E [\forall e' [e' \in E \rightarrow \exists y [BOMB(y) \& 2-ATOM(y) \& EXPLODE(y, e')]]]$

¹⁵ Note that we only claim that, in CN, the reference of a simple indefinite under the scope of a RUN may covary with that of the RUN, which is not the behavior expected of a standard distributive numeral. However, we do not claim that, in CN, a simple indefinite that scopes under a RUN must covary with respect to the RUN.

(28) Matlatzinca (Oto-Manguean)

Pu-werá **we=towá'a** tu=cháabi **nan** **pelota**
DISTR-one CL=boy 3COMP=bring.down one ball

‘Each/Every boy brought down one ball.’

Ok if each boy brought down a different ball (one ball per boy)

False if each boy brought down the same ball

(Gómez González, 2023, pp. 32–33, ex. 20b)

4.3. RUNs in Classical Nahuatl are standard distributive numerals

The two characteristics of RUNs in CN that we have just highlighted (i.e., key marking and referential covariation) receive a direct explanation if we assume that they do not mark the share in a distributive relation but rather the key. First, we can account for cases in which the RUN appears to mark the key, as in (20) and (21). Second, we can explain why RUNs can induce the covariation of a simple indefinite, as in (21) and (26). Following Gil (1995, p. 326), quantifiers that mark the key in a distributive relation are always universal. In this sense, note that universal quantifiers commonly induce referential variability of a simple indefinite in natural languages (Gil, 1995, pp. 322–344; Kuhn, 2019, pp. 5–8). For example, in Spanish, the universal quantifier *cada* ‘every’ marks the key in a distributive relation and can induce the covariation of a simple indefinite, as in (29). Thus, if RUNs in

By contrast, note in (28) that, in Matlatzinca, *puwerá* always seems to induce the covariation of a simple indefinite under its scope. To account for this fact, Gómez González (2023) follows Gil’s (1995) proposal and argues that *puwerá* is a distributive-key universal quantifier. According to Gil (1995, p. 322), a distributive-key universal quantifier always scopes over a simple indefinite, which allows but do not require the covariation between the reference of the simple indefinite and that of the distributive-key universal quantifier. Thus, scope alone do not explain directly why (28) is false when each boy brought down one and the same ball. To further illustrate this, consider the following Spanish sentence where the distributive-key universal quantifier *cada* occurs in subject position, just like *puwerá* in (28): *cada niño escogió un número* ‘each/every child chose a/one number’. Consider now a reading of this Spanish sentence under which the distributive-key universal NP *cada niño* ‘each/every child’ scopes over the simple indefinite *un número* ‘a/one number’: $\forall x [\text{CHILD}(x) \ \& \ \text{ATOM}(x) \rightarrow \exists y [\text{NUMBER}(y) \ \& \ \text{PICKED}(x, y)]]$. Note that this reading allows covariation between the reference of *cada niño* and that of *un número*, so that the formula may be true if each child picked a different number. Nonetheless, this need not be the case: the same wide scope reading of *cada niño* may also be true if each child picked the same number (see, for instance, Scontras *et al.*, 2017, p. 3). Thus, with respect to (28), an analysis under which *puwerá* is a wide scope distributive-key universal quantifier in principle, should not rule out the truth of (28) in a context where each boy brought down the same ball. Note that this has no implication on whether the example is indeed unacceptable for any reasons other than scope, which certainly deserves further research.

CN serve as key markers and, therefore, are universal quantifiers, we can directly explain why they can induce referential covariation.

(29) **Cada hombre** cargó tres maletas
 every man.MASC carry.PST three suitcase.FEM.PL

‘Every man carried three suitcases’

Interpretation: For every x , if x is a man, there is a group X of (possibly different) three suitcases and x carried X .

$\forall x [\text{MAN}(x) \ \& \ \text{ATOM}(x) \rightarrow \exists y [\text{SUITCASE}(y) \ \& \ 3\text{-ATOM}(y) \ \& \ \text{CARRY}(x, y)]]$

Nevertheless, although the previous data suggest that the reduplicated unitary cardinal in CN does not behave as expected from a distributive numeral, in this paper, we will argue that the RUN of CN is a standard distributive numeral that always marks the share in a distributive relation and, thus, it is always interpreted as if it were within the scope of a distributive operator. To support our claim, we first show that the predictions of an analysis of the RUN as a universal quantifier marking the key are incorrect. Second, we propose an alternative analysis in which we assume the presence of a null distributive operator that explains the referential covariation of indefinites. Additionally, we show how our analysis accounts for all cases in which a RUN appears.

When several key markers appear in the same clause, the distributive relations are always multiplied. This multiplication is explained by the fact that the quantifiers marking the key are universal: when they occur multiple times, these quantifiers are nested within each other in such a way that one falls under the scope of the other (Kuhn, 2019, pp. 7–8). To illustrate this, consider example (30), where the Spanish quantifier *cada* ‘every’ appears twice in the sentence. As previously explained, Spanish *cada* is a universal quantifier that marks the key of a distributive relation. Note that each occurrence of *cada* necessarily introduces a distributive relation; thus, there are two distributive relations in (30). In the distributive relation introduced by *cada mañana* ‘every morning’, the key is a plurality of mornings, and the share is a plurality of events of petting my cats. In turn, in the distributive relation introduced by *cada uno de mis gatos* ‘each of my cats’, the key is a plurality of cats, and the share is a plurality of events of petting the cat in question. In this sense, the

meaning of (30) could be paraphrased as follows: ‘For every morning, it is the case that for each one of my cats, I pet him.’ Consequently, in the context of (30), 21 events of petting occur over the course of a week ($7 \times 3 = 21$).

(30) Context: I have three cats.

Cada mañana acaricio a **cada uno** de
 every morning.FEM pet.PRES.S1SG DOM every one.MASC of
 mis gatos
 my.PL cat.MASC.PL
 ‘Every morning, I pet every one of my cats’
 $\forall x \forall y$ [MORNING(x) & MY-CAT(y) & ATOM(y) \rightarrow PET(I,y,x)]

By contrast, the occurrence of more than one distributive numeral in the same clause does not necessarily multiply distributive relations (Kuhn, 2019, pp. 7–8; Rushiti; Dobrovie-Sorin, 2024, pp. 915–916; Chapa Barrios, 2025, pp. 233–236). For instance, in (31), there are two distributive numerals and only one distributive relation between a plurality of events and two pluralities of individuals: one of men and one of boxes. In (31), for each event, there are two men and three boxes.

(31) Korean

Namca twu-myeng-ssik-i sangca sey-kay-ssik-ul
 man two-CL-DISTR-NOM box three-CL-DISTR-ACC
 wunpanhayssta
 carried
 ‘Two men carried three boxes on each occasion’
 (Oh, 2006, p. 26, ex. 7a apud Kuhn, 2019, p. 8, ex. 25)
 $\exists E \forall e$ [$e \in E \rightarrow \exists x$ [MAN(x) & 2-ATOM(x)] & $\exists y$ [SUITCASE(y) & 3-ATOM(y)] & CARRY(x, y, e)]

RUNS in CN seem to behave like distributive numerals when they occur multiple times within the same clause. In other words, the repeated appearance of a RUN does not always multiply the distributivity. Consider example (32): here, we find three instances of a RUN: *in se:senme?* ‘each one’, *se:sema:kalli t̃lao:lli* ‘one canoe of maize for each one’, and

se:sema:kalli eṯ ‘one canoe of beans for each one.’ In this example, *in se:senme?* expresses the plurality to whom the canoes of maize and beans are given. If RUNs behaved as key markers and thus as universal quantifiers, we would expect a reading with at least three distributive relations. The resulting interpretation could be paraphrased as follows: ‘to each person, Ahuizotl gave each of the canoes of maize and each of the canoes of beans.’ However, this does not appear to be the most plausible interpretation. In our interpretation of (32), there is only one distributive relation: ‘to each person, Ahuizotl gave one canoe of maize and one of beans.’ Note that the corresponding passage in the Spanish version matches this interpretation. In other words, the distributive relations are not multiplied, even though we find multiple occurrences of RUNs. Thus, in CN, when RUNs occur more than once within the same clause, they behave like distributive numerals rather than key markers.

- (32) no ioan in quinmacac tilmatl, in cecenme, cecenquimilli in tochpanecaiotl: ioan cecem acalli tlaolli, ioan cecemacalli etl

no:	i:-wa:n	in	k-in-makak	tilma?ṯli
also	POSR.3SG-with	DET	O.3-O.PL-give.PFVO	blanket.ABS
in	se:~sen-me?		se:~sen-kimilli	in
DET	DISTR~one-PL		DISTR~one-twenty-ABS	DET
to:tṯpane:kajo:tṯ	i:-wa:n		se:~sem-a:kal-li	
Tochpan.thing.ABS	POSR.3SG-with		DISTR~one-canoe-ABS	
tṯao:lli	i:wa:n		se:~sem-a:kal-li	
shelled.maize.ABS	POSR.3SG-with		DISTR~one-canoe.ABS	
eṯ				
bean.ABS				

‘also, besides that, he (Ahuizotl) gave them (the merchants) blankets, twenty Tochpan blankets to each one, and, besides that, to each one a canoe of shelled maize and a canoe of beans’ (FC09, Sahagún, 1959, p. 6, f. 5r)

Non-sensical reading: $\forall x$ [MERCHANT(x) & ATOM(x) \rightarrow $\forall y\forall z$ [MAIZE(y) & 1-BOATLOAD(y) & BEANS(z) & 1-BOATLOAD(z) \rightarrow GIVE(Ahuizotl, y, x) & GIVE(Ahuizotl, z, x)]]

Natural reading: $\forall x$ [MERCHANT(x) & ATOM(x) \rightarrow $\exists y \exists z$ [MAIZE(y) & 1-BOATLOAD(y) & BEANS(z) & 1-BOATLOAD(z) & GIVE(Ahuitzotl, y, x) & GIVE(Ahuitzotl, z, x)]] \Leftrightarrow

In (33), we present another analogous example, now with a universal quantifier *no:wia:n* ‘everywhere’ and two phrases with RUNS: *se:sentetl̄... in siwa:teo:kalli* ‘one temple of the goddesses in each’ and *se:sentlaʔfilakalpan* ‘each neighborhood’. In (33), *no:wia:n* and *se:sentlaʔfilakalpan* express the locations where the referents of *se:sentetl̄... in siwa:teo:kalli* are located. If RUNS were key markers and therefore universal quantifiers, we would expect an interpretation such as ‘in every place, in every neighborhood, each one of the goddesses’ temples was present.’ This interpretation is not plausible, since it is not physically viable: all the temples cannot be in every neighborhood at the same time. Therefore, it does not seem that the RUNS in (33) introduce multiple distributive relations. On the other hand, if the RUN is a standard distributive numeral, we can expect an interpretation like ‘in every place, in every neighborhood, there was one of the goddesses’ temples.’ This second reading is more plausible and is the one we assign to (33).

- (33) *noviian cecentetl māca, in çioateucalli, cecentlaxilacalpā: vnca:n in omaxac*
no:wia:n **se:~sen-te-tl̄** **manka**
 everywhere DISTR~one-CL-ABS be.spread.out.PST
in **siwa:teo:kalli** **se:~sen-tlaʔfilakal-pan** **onka:n**
 DET goddess.house.ABS DISTR-one-neighborhood-on there
 in oʔmafak
 DET at.crossroad
 ‘everywhere there was a temple of the goddesses, in each neighborhood, there at the crossroads’ (FC04, Sahagún, 1979a, p. 41, f. 27v)
 Non-sensical reading: $\forall x \forall y$ [PLACE(x) & ATOM(x) & TEMPLE(y) & ATOM(y) \rightarrow BE-IN(y, x)]
 Natural reading: $\forall x$ [PLACE(x) & ATOM(x) \rightarrow $\exists y$ [TEMPLE(y) & 1-ATOM(y) & BE-IN(y, x)]] \Leftrightarrow

In sum, RUNS in CN do not necessarily introduce multiple distributive relations when they occur several times within the same clause. This behavior is what one would expect

from a distributive numeral, but not from a key marker. Therefore, in our view, RUNs in CN are not quantifiers marking the key but rather standard distributive numerals. If, as we argue, the RUNs of CN are not key markers but distributive numerals, we must seek an alternative explanation for the two apparently anomalous behaviors we have been highlighting from the beginning, which we repeat in (34):

- (34) a. In some cases, the RUN seems to mark the key of a distributive relation and not the share.
b. When within the scope of a RUN, the reference of a simple indefinite can covary with that of the RUN.

Next, we develop what we believe to be the most suitable analysis to account for these two puzzles.

5. THE SEMANTICS OF REDUPLICATED UNITARY NUMERALS IN CLASSICAL NAHUATL

In this section, we develop an analysis of the meaning of RUNs in CN. To do so, we first introduce our main theoretical assumptions (§5.1). Then, we demonstrate how these assumptions are implemented to account for the behavior of RUNs in CN (§5.2) in various contexts. It is worth noting that our proposal is not conclusive and other alternative analysis, such as the one in Champollion (2016a; 2016b), could fit well with the CN data. The purpose of our formal analysis is simply to show how we could account for all cases of RUNs by assuming that they are share markers, as expected from a standard distributive numeral. However, further research is needed to assess what the best way of formalizing the data is.

5.1. *Three assumptions*

Our analysis relies on three assumptions. First, we assume that distributive relations in CN can be introduced by a null distributive operator, as proposed in other studies (Oh, 2001, 2006, pp. 48–76; Rushiti; Dobrovie-Sorin, 2024, pp. 908–916). This null distributive operator is a universal quantifier over the set of entities (events or individuals) among

which the expression in the scope of the operator is distributed.¹⁶ Second, we propose that reduplicated numerals in CN must be interpreted within the scope of a distributive operator.¹⁷ By contrast, non-reduplicated numerals are not necessarily interpreted within the scope of the null distributive operator (Oh, 2001, 2006, pp. 48–76; Rushiti; Dobrovie-Sorin, 2024).¹⁸ Third, we posit that in CN, reduplication in numerals necessarily marks the referential covariation of the numeral with respect to the entities quantified by the distributive operator, whereas the absence of reduplication allows but does not require covariation.¹⁹ This same analysis has been argued for numerals with distributivity markers in other languages (Farkas, 1997; Rushiti; Dobrovie-Sorin, 2024).

As for our first assumption, it is important to point out that the existence of a null operator is justified not only in clauses with a distributive interpretation where a reduplicated numeral appears, but also in cases where there is no explicit marker of distributivity, yet a distributive interpretation seems to arise. In these latter clauses, it is necessary to assume the presence of a null distributive operator that forces a distributive reading. To illustrate this, consider examples (35) and (36) below. In the interpretations we find most plausible, (35) has a reading that could be paraphrased as ‘one root for every two or three people’, while (36) is interpreted as ‘five prayers per day’. To obtain this reading,

¹⁶ We assume that the null distributive operator requires the distributive key to be a plurality (a sum of individuals or events), as Oh (2001: p. 340; 2006: p. 51) proposes.

¹⁷ We adopt the analysis of Rushiti and Dobrovie-Sorin (2024) for distributive numerals in Albanian. According to these authors, the distributional requirement of a distributive numeral is encoded by an uninterpretable syntactic feature [uDIST] that is checked against the interpretable feature [iDIST] carried by a distributive operator. For this agreement operation to take place, the distributive operator must c-command the distributive numeral and be local to it (i.e. the upward agree operation is clause-bounded). By contrast, non-distributive numerals do not carry the [uDIST] feature. Here we assume the same for CN reduplicated and non-reduplicated numerals: reduplicated numerals carry the [uDIST] syntactic feature, whereas non-reduplicated numerals do not.

¹⁸ Given that we assume that RUNs need to covary with respect to another variable, RUNs qualify as dependent indefinites in the sense of Farkas (1997). However, it is worth noting that, regarding our second assumption, Farkas (1997, ex. 43-44, 47-48) claims that, in Hungarian, dependent indefinites do not always occur as part of the nuclear scope of a quantifier and can also appear in its restrictor. According to Farkas, dependent indefinites are acceptable as long as its reference covaries with respect to that of a variable bound by a quantifier. This could explain why, in some cases, RUNs seem to introduce the key in CN, since they would not be limited to the scope of a distributive operator. Nonetheless, we do not follow Farkas (1997) in this regard, for, if we did so, we would miss the typological insights of Gil (1982), who claims that distributive numerals always mark the share (that is, they always occur as part of the scope of a distributive operator).

¹⁹ We also assume that the covariation requirement is lexically encoded in the reduplicated numeral. Non-reduplicated numerals do not impose such a restriction.

we need an operator that introduces the distributive relationship, but in neither example is there a form that explicitly does this.

- (35) in ce tlanelhoatl, vme tlacatl, anoço ei tlacatl itech monequj
in se: tlanelwaṯ o:me ṯla:kaṯ aʔnoso e:ji
DET one root.ABS two person/man.ABS or.perhaps three
ṯla:kaṯ i:-teṯ mo-neki
person/man.ABS POSR.3SG-beside REFL.2/3-want
‘A root (of the *oquichpahtli* plant) is enough for two or three persons’
(FC11, Sahagún, 1963, p. 183, f. 173v)

There is a plurality of men X such that for every x , if x is a member of X , x measures two or three atoms and there is a y that measures one atom and is a root and x needs y .

$\exists X \forall x [x \in X \rightarrow 2\text{-ATOM}(x) \vee 3\text{-ATOM}(x) \ \& \ \exists y [1\text{-ATOM}(y) \ \& \ \text{ROOT}(y) \ \& \ \text{NEED}(y, x)]]$

- (36) In cemilhuatl macuilpa ninoteochihua
in sem-ilwi-ṯ ma:kwil-pa ni-no-teo:ṯi:wa
DET one-day-ABS five-time S.1SG-REFL.1SG-pray
‘I pray five times a day’ (Carochi, 2001[1645], p. 388, f. 106)

There is a plurality E of events such that for every e , if e is a member of E , then e measures one day and there is an event e' such that e' is a member of E and e' is contiguous to e and there is a plurality of praying events E' that measures five atoms such that E' is temporally included in e .

$\forall e [1\text{-DAY}(e) \rightarrow \exists E [5\text{-ATOM}(E) \ \& \ \forall e' [e' \in E \rightarrow \text{PRAY}(e')] \ \& \ E \subseteq_{\text{TEMPORALLY}} e]$

Note that examples (35–36) are all cases in which the share is distributed over non-atomic entities. Thus, those examples would only contribute evidence for a silent Part-like operator (see Champollion, 2016a; 2016b). However, in CN, covert distributivity can also be over atomic individuals, as shown in the following example. In (37), individual portions of amaranth seed dough measuring four mouthfuls are distributed over the atomic members of a plurality made up of slaves.²⁰

²⁰ Now, following Champollion (2016a; 2016b), CN reduplicated numerals seem to overtly code only the Part operator, since they mark a share that distributes over atomic (32) and non-atomic entities (i). In (i), entities whose monetary value equals 2 *tomines* are distributed over non-atomic occasions separated by periods of

- (37) in quinqualtiaia nauhcamatl
 in k-in-k^waltia:-ja-? na:w-kama-tġ
 DET O.3-O.PL-eat.CAUS-PST.IPFV-S.PL four-mouthful-ABS
 ‘What they (the priests) fed them (the slaves) was four mouthfuls (of amaranth seed dough with honey) each’
 There is a plurality of individual slaves X such that for every x , if x is a member of X and x is an atom, then there is a y which measures four mouthfuls, is amaranth seed dough with honey, and is fed to x by the priests.
 $\exists X \forall x [x \in X \ \& \ \text{ATOM}(x) \rightarrow \exists y [4\text{-MOUTHFUL}(y) \ \& \ \text{FED}(\text{tz.PRIESTS}(z), y, x)]]$
 (FC09, Sahagún, 1959, p. 63, f. 45r)

Regarding our second assumption (i.e., the need to interpret reduplicated numerals within the scope of a distributive operator), we refer back to examples (32–33), where we showed that, at least in the case of RUNs, reduplicated numerals cannot be interpreted as the restrictor of a distributive operator. If this were the case, in examples where more than one RUN is present, we would expect the distributive relations to multiply, which does not occur. In our analysis, we expand our proposal of a silent distributive operator with scope over all reduplicated numerals in CN (not just RUNs). As we will see, by assuming the presence of a distributive operator, we can explain all cases where we find reduplicated numerals, both unitary and nonunitary ones.

Finally, we turn to our last assumption: reduplication in numerals necessarily marks the referential covariation of the numeral with respect to the entities over which the distributive operator quantifies, whereas the absence of reduplication allows for covariation but does not require it. In this regard, it is important to mention that in all

180 days. Thus, it seems that in CN it is only necessary to assume the existence of the Part operator. Of course, further work is needed to substantiate this claim.

- (i) monequi chicuhnauhpovalticca oume domin macoz yn donjuán
 mo-neki [tġjk^wna:w-po:wal-ti-ka]_{KEY} [o:~o:me tomin
 REFL.2/3-want nine-twenty-LIG-INSTR DISTR~two tomin
 mako:-s in don Xuan]_{SHARE}
 give.PASIV-FUT DET don Juan
 ‘It is required that, every 180 days, two tomines be given to Don Juan’
 (Anderson; Berdan; Lockhart., 1976, p. 150, doc. 26)

clauses with a distributive interpretation in our corpus, the reference of a numeral — whether reduplicated or not— covaries with that of another plurality, namely, the one over which the distributive operator quantifies (which we assume is composed either of individuals or events). However, we have data from other languages that support this hypothesis. For example, in Albanian, unmarked numerals may or may not covary with respect to the variable bound by an overt distributive operator such as *secili* ‘each’ (38a). By contrast, distributive *nga*-numerals necessarily covary (38b) (Rushiti; Dobrovie-Sorin, 2024, pp. 891–892). Note also that, cross-linguistically, this behavior is not only attested for distributive/unmarked numerals under the scope of an overt distributive operator (such as *secili* in (38)). For instance, in Korean, the unmarked numeral *seykaylul* may or may not covary with the variable bound by the non-overt distributive operator, as in (39). However distributive *ssik*-numerals, always covary with respect to the non-overt distributive operator (31, 39) (Oh, 2001). Thus, typological evidence confirms the plausibility of our third assumption.

(38) Albanian

- a. **Secili** fëmijë la-u **dy** këlysh të bardhë.
 each child wash-PST.3SG two puppies AGR white
 ‘Each child washed two white puppies (each>two; two>each).’
 ✓ There are two white puppies such that each of the children washed those two puppies
 ✓ Each child washed two (possibly different) puppies.
- b. **Secili** fëmijë la-u **nga dy** këlysh të bardhë.
 each child wash-PST.3SG nga two puppies AGR white
 ‘Each child washed two white puppies (each>two; *two>each).’
 ✗ There are two white puppies such that each of the children washed those two puppies
 ✓ Each child washed two (possibly different) puppies.
 (Rushiti; Dobrovie-Sorin, 2024, p. 892, ex. 5a-b)²¹

²¹ We could not find the meaning of the gloss AGR in Rushiti and Dobrovie-Sorin (2024).

(39) Korean

saram **twu-myeng-ssik-i** kabang **sey-kay-lul** wunpanha-ess-ta
man two-CL-DIST-NOM suitcase three-CL-ACC carry-PAST-DEC

lit. ‘Two men-Dist carried three suitcases’

Possible interpretations of (39):

✓ There is a set X of three suitcases and for every x of X , there is a set Y of two men and there is an event e such that Y carried x in e (no covariation between *seykaylul* and the distributive operator)

✓ There is an event e such that for every subevent e' of e there is a set Y of two men and there is a set X of three suitcases and Y carried X in e' (possible covariation between *seykaylul* and the distributive operator)

(Oh, 2001, p. 334, ex. 13-14)

5.2. Explaining the behavior of RUNS in Classical Nahuatl

First, our analysis accounts for expected cases in which RUNS do not seem to mark the key of the distributive relation but rather the share, as expected from a standard distributive numeral. For example, consider the clause in (40), in which a gourd of cacao is distributed to each member of a plurality. According to our analysis, in (40), a null distributive operator introduces a distributive relation. This operator quantifies over a plurality of individual messengers, such that, for every messenger, there is a gourd of cacao that is given to the messenger. Thus, the key is a plurality of individuals, and the RUN marks the share. Note that the RUN is within the scope of the distributive operator, and its reference covaries according to the plurality of individuals that constitute the key.

(40) cecenxicalpechtli in quinmacaque cacaoatl

se:~sen-ſi:kalpetſ-tli in k-in-makak-e? kakawatſ
DISTR~one-gourd-ABS DET O.3-O.PL-give.PFVO-S.PL cacao.ABS

‘what they (the Mexica) gave of cacao to each of them (the messengers) was one gourd’

(FC12, Sahagún, 1975, p. 95, f. 62r)

There is a plurality X of messengers, such that, for every x , if x is a member of X and x is an atom, then there is one gourd of cacao y and the Mexica gave y to x

$\exists X \forall x [x \in X \ \& \ \text{ATOM}(x) \rightarrow \text{MESSENGER}(x) \ \& \ \exists y [\text{CACAO-GOURD}(x) \ \& \ \text{GAVE}(\text{Iz.MEXICA}(z), y, x)]]$

Second, our analysis also accounts for cases in which a RUN seems to induce the covariation of an indefinite within its scope. In such cases, we propose that it is not the RUN but rather the null distributive operator that is responsible for the referential variability exhibited by the indefinites. For example, in (41), the null distributive operator quantifies over a plurality of events such that a cardinality predicate (*se:semilwitl*) applies to every subevent of this plurality, and, for every subevent, there is a plurality of groups of three (*e:a:kalli*) or four canoes (*na:wa:kalli*), which can be different. In this way, the key is a plurality of events and the RUN *se:semilwitl* is interpreted as if it were in the scope of a distributive operator, which, in (41), is null and induces the covariation of the indefinites *e:a:kalli* and *na:wa:kalli*. Note that, because it is a universal quantifier, the null distributive operator can indeed induce the covariation of an indefinite, as expected of this type of quantifier.

- (41) in cecemilhuitl popoliuia, ačo eacalli anočo naoacalli
in **se:~sem-ilwi-tl** po?~poliwia a?so
 DET DISTR~one-day-ABS PLR~finish.PST.IPFV perhaps
e:-a:kali-li ano?so **na:w-a:kali-li**
 three-canoe-ABS or.perhaps four-canoe-ABS
 ‘Everyday, perhaps three canoes (of water) or perhaps four canoes (of water) were consumed’ (FC09, Sahagún, 1959, p. 48, f. 38r)
 Interpretation 1: There is plurality *Y* of three of four canoes and there is a plurality *E* of events such that for every *e*, if *e* is a member of *E*, then *e* measures one day, there is an event *e'* such that *e'* is a member of *E*, *e'* is contiguous to *e*, and there is an event *e''* such that *Y* is consumed in *e''* and *e''* is temporally included ($\subseteq_{\text{TEMPORALLY}}$) in *e*.
 $\exists Y [3\text{-CANOES}(Y) \vee 4\text{-CANOES}(Y) \ \& \ \text{WATER}(Y)] \ \& \ \exists E \forall e [e \in E \rightarrow 1\text{-DAY}(e) \ \& \ \exists e' [e' \in E \ \& \ e' <_{\text{CONTIGUOUS}} e] \ \& \ \exists e'' [\text{CONSUMED}(Y, e'') \ \& \ e'' \subseteq_{\text{TEMPORALLY}} e]]$ ²²
 Interpretation 2: There is a plurality *E* of events such that for every *e*, if *e* is a member of *E*, then *e* measures one day, there is an event *e'* such that *e'* is a member of *E*, *e'*

²² We model CONTIGUITY ($<_{\text{CONTIGUOUS}}$) as a precedence relation that holds between a set of events *E* just in case there is an isomorphism $f: \langle E, <_{\text{CONTIGUOUS}} \rangle \rightarrow \langle T, < \rangle$, where *T* is a set of temporal segments.

(i) CONTIGUITY
 $\forall e \forall e': e \in E \ \& \ e' \in E. e <_{\text{CONTIGUOUS}} e' \leftrightarrow f(e) < f(e') \ \& \ \neg \exists f(e''): f(e) < f(e'') < f(e')$

is contiguous to e , there is plurality Y of three or four canoes, and there is an event e'' such that Y is consumed in e'' and e'' is temporally included in e \Rightarrow

$\exists E \forall e [e \in E \rightarrow 1\text{-DAY}(e) \ \& \ \exists e' [e' \in E \ \& \ e' <_{\text{CONTIGUOUS}} e] \ \& \ \exists Y [3\text{-CANOES}(Y) \vee 4\text{-CANOES}(Y) \ \& \ \text{WATER}(Y)] \ \& \ \exists e'' [\text{CONSUMED}(Y, e'') \ \& \ e'' \subseteq_{\text{TEMPORALLY}} e]]$

Finally, our analysis also accounts for cases in which the RUN seems to mark the key rather than the share in a distributive relation, as in (42–43). In (42), we argue that the RUN is part of the share that is distributed among the plurality of events quantified by the null distributive operator: each subevent of that plurality measures one day, is contiguous to one another, and, in each of these subevents, a rain event occurs.

(42) *cēcemilhuitl in quiahui*

se:~sem-ilwitl in kiawi
DISTR~one-day DET rain

‘Everyday/Daily is the way that it rains’ (Carochi, 2001[1645], p. 390, f. 107)

There is a plurality E of events such that for every e , if e is a member of E , then e measures one day, there is an event e' such that e' is a member of E , e' is contiguous to e , and there is a rain event that it is temporally included in e

$\exists E \forall e [e \in E \rightarrow 1\text{-DAY}(e) \ \& \ \exists e' [e' \in E \ \& \ e' <_{\text{CONTIGUOUS}} e] \ \& \ \exists e'' [\text{RAIN}(e'') \ \& \ e'' \subseteq_{\text{TEMPORALLY}} e]]$

We propose the same analysis for (43), in which *se:sentetl* is apparently part of the distributive key over which the share is divided, *o:o:ntetl in kwa:wteŋ* ‘two eggs.’

(43) *oontetl in quauhtetl qujtlazque i cecentetl quauhtli*

o:~o:n-te-tl in k^wa:wteŋ ki-tla:sk-e?
DISTR~two-CL-ABS DET eagle.egg.ABS 0.3-lay.egg-S.PL
in **se:~sen-te-tl** k^wawtli
DET DISTR~one-CL-ABS eagle.ABS

‘The eggs that each eagle laid were two each.’
(FC08, Sahagún, 1979b, p. 9, f. 6v)

There is a plurality X of eagles, such that, for every x , if x is a member of X , then the cardinality of x is equal to 1 and there is a plurality y of two eggs and x laid y .

$\exists X \forall x [x \in X \rightarrow [\text{EAGLE}(x) \ \& \ 1\text{-ATOM}(x) \ \& \ \exists y [\text{EGG}(y) \ \& \ 2\text{-ATOM}(y) \ \& \ \text{LAID}(x, y)]]]$

However, in this case, we also argue that the key is a plurality of eagle individuals over which the null distributive operator quantifies. Thus, in (43), every eagle quantified by the null operator has a cardinality equal to 1 and, for each of these eagles, there is an individual consisting of two eggs, such that each eagle laid one of these egg individuals. In (43), we capture this by establishing first a phrasal distributive relation between a key composed of eagle entities and a cardinality predicate, and, second, a clausal distributive relation between a plurality of eagles and events of these eagles laying two eggs (see Gil, 1982, pp. 103–155).²³ Note that in (43) the RUN *se:senteŋ* is interpreted as part of the scope of the null distributive operator, which quantifies over a plurality of individuals.

In this section we have shown that an analysis under which RUNs are standard distributive numerals that mark the distribution share results in the right truth conditions for different types of sentences containing a RUN, such as (40–43). Our analysis of (40–43) follows from Gil’s (1982, pp. 123) grammatical relations hierarchy. According to Gil (1982, pp. 123), distributive relations are constrained by the grammatical function of the constituents among which distribution applies: distribution of a constituent A over a constituent B is strongly disfavored if A is hierarchically higher than B. In the absence of a higher constituent, the highest constituent can only distribute phrasally over its own head, a cover or overt classifier that denotes units of some kind (Gil, 1982, pp. 107–117). This is what happens in cases such as (41–43). In (43), the subject NP is higher than the object NP, which rules out the distribution of *in se:senteŋ kwawŋi* ‘the one-one eagle’ over *o:o:nteŋ in kwa:wteŋ* ‘two-two that are eggs’, and forces the distribution of the cardinality predicate *se:senteŋ* ‘to measure one atom’ among the denotation of the NP classifier head, individual units that are eagles. The object NP *o:o:nteŋ in kwa:wteŋ* also distributes over these individual eagle units, which measure one atom. Thus, the way the meaning of (43) is composed gives the false impression of *se:senteŋ* marking the key over which the share *o:o:nteŋ in kwa:wteŋ* distributes. Based on this, we suggest that the cases in which key and

²³ It is worth noting that, in (43), the RUN *se:senteŋ* occurs as part of an agent NP that functions as the subject of the clause. According to Gil (1982, pp. 103–155), distributive numerals that occur as part of an agent NP only display phrasal distributive relations (class C); that is, they always distribute over the head of the NP.

share seem to conflate are those in which the share can only distribute phrasally over its classifier head, as in (43).²⁴ Of course, more data is needed to properly test and assess this hypothesis. As for (41–42), it is important to point out that our analysis would imply that *se:semilwitl̃* in (41–42) is structurally higher than any other constituent and can only distribute over its event-denoting classifier head.²⁵

Note also that, in cases such as (41–43), we get the same truth conditions regardless of whether we interpret the RUN as a key marker or as a share marker that phrasally distributes over its head. However, the semantic composition by which we arrive at those truth conditions differs depending on the way we interpret the RUNS in (41–43). Here, we have argued for an analysis in which CN RUNS are always share markers, since distributive relations are not multiplied when several RUNS occur in the same clause. Nonetheless, we recognize that speakers may have found sentences such as (41–43) ambiguous: in (41–43), RUNS could be interpreted either as key or share markers and, in both cases, the same truth conditions would be obtained. These types of structures in which two different semantic computations have the same truth conditions are especially interesting in diachronic terms, since they could eventually lead to a semantic change, namely the reanalysis of distributive quantifiers to universal quantifiers.²⁶ We leave for further research the fine-grained analysis of the mechanisms behind this semantic change; still, we highlight the relevance of CN RUNS as an ideal environment for advancing in the understanding of the grammaticalization path from a distributive numeral to a universal quantifier.

²⁴ Note that this also applies to example (32): *se:senme?* distributes over its own classifier head (a set of individuals) because there is no other higher constituent over which it can distribute. The only other higher is the null subject (which refers to Ahuitzotl). However, this null constituent is not a plural entity. Therefore, it cannot function as the distributive key (see note 16).

²⁵ Though we leave a full account of this for future research, we note here that cross-linguistically the behavior of *se:semilwitl̃* with regard to distribution does not seem to be surprising. In CN, *se:semilwitl̃* ‘every day’ seems to belong to the same paradigm as other distributive interval-denoting expressions like *na:na:wilwitika* <*n̄anāhuilhuitica*> ‘every four days/every fourth day’ (Carochi, 2001[1645], pp. 390–392, §5.2.11, f. 107). In fact, Carochi (2001[1645], pp. 390–392, §5.2.11, f. 107) claims that *se:semilwitl̃* <*cēcemilhuitl̃*> is synonymous to *se:semilwitika* <*cēcemilhuitica*> ‘every day’. According to Gil (1982, pp. 169–170), in Tagalog expressions such as these are distributive ordinal numerals which always distribute phrasally over its head (which, in this case, is a classifier that denotes units akin to events). Thus, as a working hypothesis, we suggest that distributive interval-denoting numerals might be analyzed as share markers that necessarily distribute over its classifier head.

²⁶ See Eckardt (2006) for the conditions under which semantic reanalysis occurs.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we presented an analysis of the semantics of reduplicated unitary numerals in Classical Nahuatl. Based on a corpus of its usage in various documents from the 16th and 17th centuries and considering the vast literature on distributivity, we have argued that in CN, RUNs are standard distributive numerals and, as such, they always mark the share and not the key of a distribution. Specifically, we propose that: 1) the distributive relation may be introduced by a null distributive operator, which is a universal quantifier over the members of a plurality; 2) RUNs must be interpreted under the scope of this null distributive operator, and their reference necessarily covaries according to the plurality over which the operator quantifies. Our analysis can account for both prototypical cases in which the RUN clearly behaves as a standard share marker and non-prototypical cases in which RUNs seem to mark the distribution key or induce referential covariation of an indefinite in the clause. Lastly, although deeper research is required, we believe that this analysis might be extended to other non-unitary reduplicated numerals in CN.

ABBREVIATIONS

1:	first person
2:	second person
3:	third person
A:	ergative set A
ABS:	absolute/absolute suffix
ACC:	accusative
CAUS:	causative
CL:	classifier
CP:	completive
COMP:	completive
DET:	determiner

DISTR:	distributive
DOM:	differential object marking
ERG:	ergative
FEM:	feminine
FUT:	future
IPFV:	imperfective
ICP:	incompletive
INCOM:	incompletive
MASC:	masculine
NOM:	nominative
O:	object
PL:	plural
POSR:	possessor
PST:	past
REFL:	reflexive
S:	subject
SG:	singular

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Conflict of Interest

The author(s) declare no competing interests.

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Statement of Data Availability

The data and materials that support the findings of this study are openly available in the electronic corpus compiled by Thouvenot and Fisher ([s.d.]). We queried all instances of the sequence <cece> in the *Florentine Codex* using Thouvenot and Fisher's ([s.d.]) corpus. From the results obtained, we selected only those corresponding to unitary distributive numerals. We excluded verbs showing reduplication of *sem-*, given that in some cases it is unclear whether the reduplication of the base /sem-/ involves a numeral meaning. Note that the form *se:senjaka*: 'every/each' falls into this excluded group, since, according to Andrews (2003, p. 440), *se:senjaka*: purportedly derives from the verbal base *senja?*- 'go as one'. Data on distributive numerals other than the unitary type are provided within the article.

AI Usage Statement

We declare that we have utilized AI tools, specifically Grammarly and Paperpal, to proofread the entire manuscript for grammar and spelling, since we are not native English speakers. These tools were not used for content generation, data analysis, or argumentation.

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CORPORA

Main Corpus

FC01 = SAHAGÚN, B. de. *General History of the Things of New Spain. Book 1: The gods*. Ed. A. J. O. Anderson; C. E. Dibble. Santa Fe: The School of American Research/the University of Utah, 1970.

FC02 = SAHAGÚN, B. de. *General History of the Things of New Spain. Book 2: The Ceremonies*. Ed. A. J. O. Anderson; C. E. Dibble. Santa Fe: The School of American Research/the University of Utah, 1981.

FC03 = SAHAGÚN, B. de. *General History of the Things of New Spain. Book 3: The Origins of the Gods*. Ed. A. J. O. Anderson; C. E. Dibble. Santa Fe: The School of American Research/the University of Utah, 1978.

- FC04 = SAHAGÚN, B. de. *General History of the Things of New Spain. Book 4: The soothsayers and Book 5: The omens*. Ed. A. J. O. Anderson; C. E. Dibble. Santa Fe: The School of American Research/the University of Utah, 1979a.
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